

EFFECTIVENESS OF LEARNING AND TEACHING INNOVATION SPECIAL EDUCATION (HEARING) THROUGH VIDEO IMPRESSIONS

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Abstract

This study aims to review the effectiveness of learning and teaching innovation special education (hearing) via video at the Polytechnic Tuanku Syed Sirajuddin, Polytechnic Special Skills Certificate (Hotel Catering) was implemented in June 2014 Semester. The sample was composed of 22 students from the Department of Tourism and Hospitality. These data are collected using a questionnaire instrument and analyzed using SPSS (statistical package for social sciences). Results of the analysis of data obtained in this study indicate that the level of understanding of special education students (hearing) at the Polytechnic Tuanku Syed Sirajuddin who teach special education students is moderate with a mean score. It is hoped that the findings of this study can serve as a guide to the management of Polytechnic Tuanku Syed Sirajuddin to evaluate the effectiveness of the video in the department involving lecturers in teaching special education students (hearing) and then take the help of various aspects of the role as described in the part of the proposal for enhance the delivery of teaching lessons to special education (hearing).

Keyword: efficacy, video and special education students (hearing)

Introduction

Globalization and technological developments in education has many challenges to educators in equipping themselves with the skills over time and current. Technology is the foundation and driving force in making Malaysia a nation of excellence by 2020. Accordingly, the educators are not left in the realization of these skills in every selfeducated students. The importance of technology in education cannot be denied and it

made the students have the knowledge without borders (Brown, 1998). However, we often overlook about education for special education students. Here, the researchers highlight the issue of special education students (hearing) in the use of technology to assist them in learning.

The use of technology to assist special education students (hearing) from various angles in terms of academic subjects like social or they can find new friends with people who are in the same boat as them and increase their competitiveness with others. Therefore, they are easier to learn and understand as well as keeping pace with others in order to progress from time to time. The existence of tools or special technology-based systems for people with disabilities (hearing) helps them to function as a member of society, which also contribute equally to the normal state.

The use of video technology in teaching and learning (P & P) This is more interactive, able to create a learning process similar to learning face to face, each session can record video conferencing and so on (SAFF 2000). According Darvina (2003), the use of video as a teaching tool not only to attract students to the teaching and learning process (P & P) to be better, but also to improve student understanding and facilitate educator or lecturer in conveying knowledge. The use of video can also encourage students in learning and help solve learning problems that existed before. Education using video technology is a new experience for special education students (hearing) at the Polytechnic Tuanku Syed Sirajuddin, Perlis.

Problem Statement

Most special education students (listeners) do not participate actively in the teaching and learning (P & P). This Scenario happens because the teaching more focused on teachers or lecturers and sign language interpreter's only .Education one way this has created problems for special education students (hearing). Ismail Yassin (2010) stated in their study that students lose focus or concentration, does not understand what is learned and sleepy during the teaching and learning (P & P) is run.

The objective of the study:

The use of video technology as an aid to teaching and learning (P & P) for special education students (hearing) was conducted at the Polytechnic Tuanku Syed Sirajuddin, Perlis. Objective this study can identify the effective use of video on the special education students (hearing) at the Polytechnic Tuanku Syed Sirajuddin from the following aspects:

1. Improving students' understanding of special (hearing) with lessons learned.
2. Improving learning more attractive to special education students (hearing).
3. Review the appropriateness of the use of video in teaching special education students (hearing).

Research question:

In the course of this study to answer the question of objectives:

1. Does the use of video to improve the understanding of special education students (hearing)?
2. Does the use of video can increase student interest in special education (hearing) in learning?
3. Does the use of video appropriate for special education students (hearing)?

Research interests:

Researchers realized that the level of understanding special education students (hearing) a major problem where the transmission of knowledge cannot be fully understood by them. The findings of this study is important and hopefully will help special education students (hearing) in their learning and can improve students' understanding of education special (hearing) is equivalent to the normal students. Researchers also want to identify the usage of video applications can be accepted by special education students (hearing) or not.

Methodology

Scope / Limitations Reviews

Involving students semester 1.2 and 4 only. The study is limited to 30 students who represented the students Special Skills Certificate (Hotel and Catering) Polytechnic Tuanku Syed Sirajuddin, Perlis.

Research design

Studies conducted in this research involved a survey using a questionnaire. Analysis of the percentage used to answer the research questions. Are special education students (loss) gain understanding of their learning with outstanding results?

Sample / Population study

The population is made up of special education students (hearing) Polytechnic Tuanku Syed Sirajuddin Perlis. The selection is random sample survey. Respondents answered the survey with the assistance of a sign language interpreter from the Department of Hospitality and Tourism, Polytechnic Tuanku Syed Sirajuddin, Perlis.

Research Instrument:

The instrument used was a questionnaire in which they provide information in terms of the overall percentage of the background and the effective use of video to increase understanding of the special education students (hearing). All data and information collected and analyzed using the items listed.

A pilot study

A pilot study was conducted on 10 respondents from special education students (hearing) Tourism and Hospitality Department at the Polytechnic Tuanku Syed Sirajuddin, Perlis.

This pilot study is used to identify the reliability of the questionnaire, to estimate the time to explain, time to run, time to answer and problems which may arise from the research. Based on the analysis of the pilot study has been made, the Cronbach Alpha (α) obtained is 0.90, and it was on a high level. This shows that the reliability of the questionnaire can be used and need not be changed.

Findings

The results obtained are recorded in the form of tables, graphs and analysis for each question as well. This analysis evaluated the effectiveness of using video to enhance students' understanding of special education (hearing) in their learning. Descriptive analysis of the percentage used to raise the percentage of respondents to the consensus of opinion questions.

Analysis of data from Part A of the questionnaire that was conducted revealed that the background of the respondents in this study, it was found that 8 special education students (hearing) male and 22 female students. Of respondents aged 17-19 years, a total of 27 people, 20-25 years old, consisting of 2 people and more than 26 years of age is one person only.

Analysis of data from Part B of the questionnaire was carried out as described in

Table 1 - Percentage of the learning process via video.

ITEM	QUESTION	PERCENTAGE
Motivation	The process of learning through video conferencing to increase my motivation to learn.	100%
	I am more motivated to learn through video conferencing.	97%
Attention	Environment in a video played a key role in learning.	70%
	In a video conference session, I gave careful attention to the explanation / demonstration lectures.	93%
	Video screening session that is expected to help improve performance in my learning.	97%

Acquisition Memory Back

Video presentation helped me to recall what they have learned.	100%
Through video conferencing sessions I can acquire knowledge that is not available in the module.	98%

Perception selection

In a video conference session, I was able to distinguish the important and relevant information from the less important.	86%
I'd better pay attention to stimuli (pictures) because it helps me understand the lesson more effectively.	85%

Encode and Long-Term Storage

I can only remember the information received during the video conference session	100%
Knowledge I have learned through the afternoon session videos, I will compare with other learning materials.	97%

Response / Achievement

I showed changes with better performance in the learning process if I attend a video conference.	92%
I am quite confident to take part in a video conference session.	98%

Feedback and Affirmation

Feedback can be provided with clearer in learning through video conferencing	100%
I also responded promptly to the questions raised by lectures.	90%

Generalization

What is learned in the video helped me to learn with other learning materials.	100%
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The learning process is applicable to the use of this technology based learning approach Gagne (1985). Researchers have used the learning process Gagne (1985), where items such as motivation, attention, memory acquisition back, choice of perception, encoding and long-term storage, response / performance, feedback and reinforcement and generalization / transfer of learning in order to assess the effectiveness of the use of video help improve the understanding of special education students (hearing) at the Department of Tourism and Hospitality, Polytechnic Tuanku Syed Sirajuddin, Perlis.

Referring to item 1 in the motivation phase, 100% of respondents recorded the agreement to increase motivation. For item 2, 97% of students agree that they are more motivated to learn through video. Next, for the attention, 70% of students agreed that the environment in a video conference played an important role to education and followed by 93% of respondents could give careful attention to lighting lecturer. 97% of respondents agreed that the sessions helped improve the performance of video respondent.

In the acquisition phase memory back, as much as 100% of respondents said that video conferencing sessions to help them recall what they have learned. While 98% of respondents said that video conferencing sessions to assist them in acquiring knowledge that is not contained in the material in the module.

For the selection phase of perception, a total of 86% of respondents agreed that they were able to distinguish the important and relevant information from the less important. This phase also showed that 85% of respondents agree that they can be better member of sign language stimulation. This helps the respondent understand the lessons more effectively. Next, the phase encoding and long-term storage, 100% of respondents agreed that they could considering the information received during the video conference and even 97% of respondents were able to compare the knowledge learned with other learning materials.

The percentage of phase response and performance shows 92% of respondents agree that they show changes with better performance and 98% of respondents believe that they are confident enough to take part in a video conference sessions than conventional learning.

For the phase of feedback and reinforcement, even if 100% of respondents agreed that feedback can be provided with clearer in video conferencing sessions. The findings show that respondents believe the feedback provided in a video conference session is high. Meanwhile, 90% of respondents agreed that they had responded promptly to the questions raised by lectures. Next, the generalization phases showed that 1000% of respondents agree what is learned in video conferencing sessions to help them learn with other learning materials.

Overall, it was found that the percentage listed in Table 1 shows that more than 90% of respondents agree with all the questions raised. This shows that the use of video not only to attract students to the teaching and learning processes but help to improve students' understanding. Therefore, the learning process of special education students (hearing) is applied through the use of video conferencing technology.

Discussion

Summary of the findings

Improve the effectiveness of teaching and learning process. Making use of video as a medium to deliver the knowledge that can make a teaching and learning process more effective. Facilitate student understanding of the use of media in understanding the content of teaching delivered by teachers or lecturers. Special education students can learn individually and collectively without requiring their teachers as well. Ahmad, Rozhan and Abdul Rahman (1999) has stated that the use of video is more effective than traditional classroom-based educators only. Students are more motivated by a change in teaching and learning (P & P). Enthusiasm for learning is increasing and more concentration can be given during the learning process.

Sukono (2002), the use of technology can make up skills more quickly and effectively. In learning a physical skill like using computer software, skills doing experiments, handling tools and so requires training. Therefore the use of video provides an opportunity for special education students (hearing) in the master using this technology. Special education students (hearing) is also able to master and control the information that they want to learn at their own convenience. This learning process gives them the opportunity to repeating the related video without hindrance from anyone. Indirectly enable the process of learning takes place according to the needs and students' acceptance and not according to the needs of teachers and lecturers alone. They also do not feel left out and they do not feel they have a deficiency in comparison with many students.

The teaching process is faster on the video display. This is because the process is lengthy explanations and demonstrations that drag on inevitably. This is because the process through video description has combined elements such as images, language and background noise signals which indirectly provides a clearer explanation to the students of special education (hearing).

According Tiene (1997) promises freedom of virtual education raising science. Special education students (hearing) have equal opportunities to students to learn something normal in science. With the use of their technology can achieve knowledge comparable to other normal person. For example you can learn basic things in teaching. Advantages of using video in education technology to overcome space, time and the senses for the disabled. Disadvantages that may be difficult for them to learn with this technology can help them be able to attend classes on a par with normal students.

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